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Oil Drilling Technology

Introduction

Many oil deposits worldwide are increasing in importance as a safe future supply of energy. It is estimated that heavy oil as a resource is available in trillions of barrels worth, but only billions of barrels have been recovered to date. The realization of the full latent and the assurance of heavy oil depend on technology evolution around the recovery process appropriate for a broad array of oil-phase situation and reservoir. The technologies have to be comparatively environmentally benign. This paper compares traditional methods of oil production to current steam flooding methods.

Comparison between Traditional and Modern Oil Extraction Methods

The extraction of oil has been growing and evolving for decades, with the least enhanced oil recovery, methods taking it to a new level, and possibly a shift. Primary oil recovery methods either tap oil naturally rising to the surface or that can be easily pumped to the surface. Primary drilling methods account for 10 percent of oil reserves in wells. Secondary oil recovery methods retrieve up to 30 percent more oil from an oil well by pumping water to propel the oil to the exterior (Al Shaibi and Al Abri 2018). Enhanced oil recovery methods include injection of gas, injection of chemical, and thermal recovery. In the injection gas, carbon dioxide, natural gas, or nitrogen s mixed with trapped oil to make it denser and push the oil to the surface. In thermal injection, steam is issued to heat oil in a reservoir to reduce its viscosity and ease oil release enabling it to glow to the surface. In chemical injection, the tension of the oil surface is lowered to allow it t flow from trapped pockets, and water flooding is used to transport the oil to the

ground level. Chemical injection remains one of the least preferred oil recovery methods since it needs secondary pumping of water to push the oil to the surface (Hama, Saleh, and Bai 2014). Enhanced oil recovery techniques are intended to alter the trapped oil state to be extracted instead of forcing it onto the surface using water pressure. After traditional oil extraction methods have been used, enhanced oil recovery methods can recover up to 60% of the oil left in a reservoir. The recovered oil forms an additional source of full that boosts global oil reserves while reducing the expenditure at the same time. With the ongoing depletion of oil reserves on the planet, more extensive research and development will be needed to improve oil recovery methods.

Non-Thermal Oil Recovery Methods

The recent decades have exhibited an upsurge in the production of heavy oil. The increase is anticipated to continue with progress into the coming years due to an anticipated deficit in conservative oil and plenty of more extensive and identified reservoirs of heavy oil. The resource is produced economically produced using the injection of water, primary recovery, and thermal-enhanced recovery (TEOR) techniques (Hama, Saleh, and Bai 2014). The Orinoco belt in Venezuela and long horizontal wells account for the most recent primary production and have been the most significant in making the venture achievable.

The resource has lowly mobile and highly viscous due to its high viscosity, despite the fact that the relative permeability is high. Consequently, the mobility ratio is not favorable in any process of fluid displacement. Using chemicals can be beneficial in two ways, assuming a minimal rock matrix loss (Alvarado and Manrique 2010). The first is that there will be a decrease in interfacial tension, which will result in lower residual saturation of oil even though there is an ineffective displacement. The other is that low tension on the surfaces promotes formation of

emulsions making effective mobility ratio favorable. The emulsion lowers the fluid displacing mobility through drop entrapment and entrainment.

In the enhanced oil recovery method, steam injection is the most used with most projects utilizing steam injection being in Venezuela, California, Canada, and Indonesia. This oil recovery method can approach up to 20 percent of cyclic steaming and more than 50% for constant steam injection. The new techniques, for instance hybrid methods and injection of solvent process are under testing for use in the recovery of heavy oil in which steam will not be used as an alternative (Mollaei and Maini 2010).

The heavy oil reservoir is very dense and does not easily flow unless the reservoir's has high temperature. As such, primary and secondary oil recovery methods are not used. These methods are bypassed if they are used, and the recovery proceeds to the enhanced recovery methods. The routes used in this case are specific to the reservoir, and when it is useful to one reservoir of heavy oil, it is not usable in another.

The recoverable oil quantity depends on the number of factors such as rock permeability, oil viscosity, and natural drive strengths regarding the gas present and the adjacent water or gravity pressure. Loose reservoir rocks such as sandstone are permeable and permit a general free flow of oil instead of tight ones as shale. Natural pressure from the surrounding rocks helps the oil flow, such as the gas dissolved in oil and gravity strength. Heavy oils have a broad viscosity range from poorly mobile materials to manageable fluids.

The extraction of heavy oil is more traditional in its application of thermal oil recovery methods where the injection of steam is mostly used. In this regard, heavy oil extraction methods encompassing thermal techniques such as steam floods, steam-assisted gravity draining, cyclic

steam stimulation, and non-thermal such as cyclic solvent process, vapor-assisted extraction of petroleum, sand production cold flow, and in situ processes.

Thermal Methods

Heavy oil is highly viscous and highly dense in comparison with conventional oil. Due to these characteristics, heavy oil and petroleum are extracted using well production techniques and enhanced recovery methods. For complete utilization of reservoir energy, both primary and secondary oil recovery methods are used in the production of conventional crude oil as heavy oil is produced using enhanced tertiary methods of oil extraction (Bagheripour, Ayatollahi and Shabaninejad 2012). Subsurface oil does not flow easily towards a wellbore, and thermal recovery is used to heat the reservoir, lower the viscosity, increase the heavy oil's mobility, and flow into the wellbore. Steam heated to high temperatures is used conventionally in heat delivery. The ratio of steam to oil to fuel is crucial in measuring the energy necessary for heavy oil extraction.

Thermal recovery methods used currently can be categorized into two classes, namely; processes where hot fluids including reservoir steam injection and methods where heat is produced in the well through a combustion process. The earlier is based on steam as the later is fire flooding or in situ combustions. The processes can also be classified as either stimulation treatments where the only storage near the extraction well is heated or thermal drives that reduce viscosity and provide the force for increased flow rates. Stimulation treatments can be combined with thermal powers, with the propelling forces being both imposed and natural (Mollaei and Maini 2010). Each method applied is situation-specific, and resource properties must be comprehended before a process is selected such as geological setting, the extent of the area, depth and resource thickness, the oil composition, its solidity and viscosity and the quantity of

gas, the amount of water at the bottom or top gas zone presence, geomechanical and petrophysical features including porosity, porosity and hardness of rocks, shale layer presence, horizontal and vertical permeability as well as property variation across the reservoir.

Thermal cracking and visbreaking as forms of thermal decomposition are utilized in reducing the heavy crude oil thickness. The crude oil intermolecular balance changes with the carbonaceous residue deposition separation from oil and leaves a lighter phase of oil product that flows smoothly (Al Shaibi and Al Abri 2018). Visbreaking, as a surface process, offers massive oil thermal recovery opportunities. Partial oil *in situ* upgrade and carbonaceous residue deposition containing the most significant part of nitrogen and metals from the oil and surface partial oil upgrade is preferred. Carbonaceous residue deposition disadvantage is that it can bring about a channel flow and pore blockage inside the reservoir. This form of interference must, therefore, be avoided.

The alteration of crude oil happens in all methods of thermal recoveries. However, the momentous conversion quantity by thermal changes happens at very high temperatures met in the heating process.

Works Cited

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